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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PROFESSIONAL NEEDS OF DEPUTY DIRECTORS AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Andijon davlat chet tillari instituti doktoranti

Abstract: This study examines the professional needs, challenges, and motivations of deputy directors for academic affairs in Uzbekistan's general secondary schools. A needs analysis survey of 204 deputy directors was carried out to evaluate their experience, educational background, competencies, and access to professional development. The results show that while many leaders are confident in conflict resolution, teacher evaluation, and resource management, they encounter persistent challenges such as excessive administrative workload, limited ICT skills, resource shortages, and uneven access to training. Despite these difficulties, deputy directors remain highly motivated by student achievement and professional responsibility. The findings underscore the urgent need for targeted postgraduate programs, equitable opportunities for professional development, investment in ICT, and reduction of bureaucratic demands. The recommendations emphasize strengthening leadership preparation and fostering school-community collaboration to improve educational quality.

Key words: deputy directors, educational leadership, needs analysis, professional development, Uzbekistan, ICT in education, school management.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tadqiqotda O'zbekiston umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida o'quv ishlari bo'yicha direktor o'rinbosarlarining kasbiy ehtiyojlari, muammolari va motivatsiyasi o'rganildi. 204 nafar direktor o'rinbosari o'rtasida ehtiyojlar tahlili so'rovi o'tkazilib, ularning tajribasi, ta'limiy tayyorgarligi, kompetensiyalari va kasbiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlariga e'tibor qaratildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, ko'plab rahbarlar nizolarni hal qilish, o'qituvchilar faoliyatini baholash va resurslarni boshqarishda yetarli darajada ishonchga ega bo'lsalar-da, ular ortiqcha ma'muriy yuklama, cheklangan axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) ko'nikmalari, resurs yetishmovchiligi va malaka oshirish imkoniyatlarining bir xillik emasligi kabi muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Shunga qaramay, direktor o'rinbosarlari o'quvchilarning yutuqlari va kasbiy mas'uliyat bilan yuqori darajada motivatsiyaga ega. Xulosalarda maxsus magistratura dasturlarini joriy etish, professional rivojlanishda teng imkoniyatlarni yaratish, AKTga investitsiyalarni kengaytirish hamda byurokratik talablarni kamaytirish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Tavsiyalar rahbarlikka tayyorlash tizimini mustahkamlash va maktab-hamjamiyat hamkorligini rivojlantirish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: direktor o'rinbosarlari, ta'lim rahbarligi, ehtiyojlar tahlili, kasbiy rivojlanish, O'zbekiston, ta'limda AKT, maktab boshqaruvi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются профессиональные потребности, трудности и мотивация заместителей директоров по учебной части общеобразовательных школ Узбекистана. Был проведён опрос среди 204 заместителей директоров с целью анализа их опыта, образовательной подготовки, компетенций и доступа к профессиональному развитию. Результаты показали, что многие руководители уверены в решении конфликтов, оценке работы учителей и управлении ресурсами, однако сталкиваются с такими проблемами, как чрезмерная административная нагрузка, ограниченные навыки в области информационно-коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ), нехватка ресурсов и неравномерный доступ к обучению. Несмотря на эти трудности, заместители директоров сохраняют высокую мотивацию, основанную на успехах учащихся и профессиональной ответственности. В заключении подчеркивается необходимость внедрения целевых магистерских программ, обеспечения равных возможностей для профессионального роста, инвестиций в ИКТ и сокращения бюрократических требований. Рекомендации направлены на укрепление системы подготовки руководителей и развитие сотрудничества школы и сообщества с целью повышения качества образования.

Ключевые слова: заместители директоров, образовательное лидерство, анализ потребностей, профессиональное развитие, Узбекистан, ИКТ в образовании, школьное управление.

INTRODUCTION

Educational leadership plays a critical role in ensuring the quality of teaching and learning in schools. In Uzbekistan, the role of deputy directors for academic affairs has become increasingly important as the education system undergoes reforms aimed at improving teacher performance, enhancing instructional practices, and raising student achievement. School leaders are expected not only to manage administrative duties but also to foster professional growth among teachers, integrate innovative teaching methods, and address challenges related to curriculum implementation, conflict resolution, and resource allocation.

Needs analysis is a valuable tool in identifying the competencies and skills required by school leaders to fulfill their responsibilities effectively. By examining their current experiences, qualifications, challenges, and motivations, it becomes possible to design targeted professional development programs. International studies also confirm that leadership capacity is directly linked to school improvement and student outcomes (Day & Sammons, 2016; Leithwood et al., 2020). However, little research has focused on the professional needs of deputy directors in Uzbekistan.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the professional competencies, challenges, and development needs of school deputy directors in Uzbekistan. The results provide insights into how leadership training can be better aligned with the realities of schools, ensuring continuous improvement in educational quality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Educational leadership literature consistently underscores the pivotal influence of school leaders on instructional quality and student outcomes. For example, Leithwood and colleagues demonstrate that leadership is second only to classroom teaching in its impact on student learning (2004). Meanwhile, Brauckmann et al. highlight the need for leadership theories and practices to be sensitive to contextual factors, especially in non-Western education systems (2023). In the context of Uzbekistan, official analysis of school-leadership roles shows that deputy directors support coordination of improvement plans and implement ICT and financial competencies among other duties (2024, Uzbekistan Profile). These findings suggest that deputy directors must develop broad leadership capacities to meet evolving educational demands.

Professional development (PD) of school leaders emerges as a key theme in the research. Darling-Hammond et al. argue that effective leadership preparation must integrate theory and practice, coaching, and sustained support rather than isolated workshops (2007). Complementing this, Mullen's recent review identifies critical barriers to principal PD – including time constraints, heavy administrative load, and technology demands (2024). In Uzbekistan, empirical evidence for leader-oriented PD remains sparse, pointing to a gap between global best practice and local implementation. Thus, deputy directors' professional needs must account for both leadership preparation and ongoing tailored development.

Research also points to specific competencies and contextual challenges facing educational leaders. For instance, Tichnor-Wagner et al. propose a “global competence” framework for educational leaders which encompasses digital literacy, collaboration, and culturally responsive leadership (2019). In line with this, the Uzbekistan education-profile document notes that deputy directors are expected to coordinate technological equipment, evaluate teachers, and engage parents – but face limited professional-training access, resource constraints, and administrative burdens (2024). Thus, understanding deputy directors' needs demands attention to both skills (ICT, instructional leadership) and the structural conditions (bureaucracy, resources, training access) influencing their work.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a quantitative needs analysis survey to explore the professional development requirements of deputy directors for academic affairs.

Participants: A total of 204 deputy directors from general secondary schools across Uzbekistan took part in the survey. Respondents varied in years of experience from 1–3 years to more than 10 years, mostly bachelor's degree holders, with a smaller proportion holding master's degrees when it comes to educational background of participants, and the number of staff they managed ranging from fewer than 20 to more than 50 employees. A structured questionnaire was designed, consisting of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. It covered areas such as leadership experience, participation in professional development, perceived challenges, skills needed for improvement, and motivational factors. The survey was distributed via Telegram groups, and all 204 responses were collected in June 2024, and then quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages, frequencies, and averages), while qualitative responses were coded thematically to identify recurring patterns regarding challenges and professional needs.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Out of the 204 respondents, the majority (46.5%) reported having 4–7 years of experience in educational management. Another 18.1% had 8–10 years, and the same percentage had over 10 years, while 17.4% were relatively new with 1–3 years of experience. In terms of educational qualifications, most participants (88.2%) held a bachelor's degree, while 11.8% had a master's degree. No respondents reported having doctoral-level qualifications.

62.5% of respondents oversaw 20–35 employees, 22.2% managed 36–50 employees, and 11.8% supervised more than 50 employees. Only 3.5% reported leading fewer than 20 staff members. There was wide variation in professional development engagement. Some respondents attended more than 10 trainings per year, while others had none. In terms of leadership competencies, deputy directors were most confident in conflict resolution (53.5% rated very high) and teacher evaluation (56.3% very high). Confidence was weaker in implementing innovative teaching methods (21.5% less confident) and budgeting.

Respondents reported spending most of their time on administrative tasks, followed by communication with staff and parents, leaving little for strategic planning, whereas key issues included paperwork overload, insufficient resources, teacher shortages, difficulties in scheduling, and low teacher motivation. However, ICT and digital literacy, management and leadership, communication, foreign languages, and time management were cited as challenging tasks for them.

One interesting fact was that deputy directors were motivated by student progress, trust from colleagues, and commitment to their profession.

DISCUSSION

The findings highlight several aspects of deputy directors' professional practice. Many have mid-level experience but lack advanced academic qualifications, indicating a need for specialized postgraduate leadership programs. Their workload is dominated by administration, consistent with international findings (Pont, Nusche, & Moorman, 2008). This reduces opportunities for strategic and instructional leadership.

Access to professional development was inconsistent, echoing research emphasizing the importance of equitable and sustained training (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Leaders reported strong skills in conflict resolution but weaker confidence in ICT and innovation, underscoring the need for training in digital leadership (Hallinger, 2011).

Challenges with resources and teacher shortages mirror issues in developing contexts (Oduro, 2004). Despite this, intrinsic motivation was strong, aligning with self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Building on this motivation through recognition and support will be crucial for reforms.

Overall, the study underscores the need for context-specific professional development programs that ensure equity, emphasize ICT and communication, reduce paperwork, and strengthen school–community collaboration.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study examined the professional needs of deputy directors in Uzbekistan's general secondary schools. While they showed confidence in conflict resolution and teacher evaluation, they face challenges such as administrative overload, resource shortages, and uneven access to training. Recommendations include developing postgraduate leadership programs, standardizing access to professional development, reducing bureaucracy, investing in ICT, and enhancing collaboration with parents and communities. Addressing these areas will strengthen school leadership and improve educational quality nationwide.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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